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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study			
Computationally unmasking each fatty acyl C=C position in complex lipids by routine LC-MS/MS lipidomics - Rampler Lab			
Document creation date	06/23/2025	Corresponding Email	evelyn.rampler@univie.ac.at
Principal investigator	Evelyn Rampler	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	Derivatization	none
pH adjustment	acetic acid	Were internal standards used?	Yes
2-phase system	BUME	Deposition method	Micropipette
Special conditions	room temperature, intensive mixing (vortexing) and sonication	Internal standards used	Avanti EquiSPLASH

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate, Formic acid	MS Level	MS ²
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Separation type 1	LC	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	High resolution
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS ²	300000
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS ²	5
MS type	QTOF	Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Profile mode
MS vendor	SCIEX	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Ion source	ESI		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Solvent blank	Type of QC sample	Commercial sample, Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	No
Lipid recovery	No	Accuracy	No
Dynamic quantification range	No	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	No		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification and identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	10.25345/C5CV4C43V	Raw data upload	Yes
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	Summary data are available as supplementary data files with the corresponding publication. C12 LILY yeast extract was used for instrument performance check, SRM 1950 was used for ZenoTOF EAD method optimization prior to sample measurement. Measurements of NIST SRM 1950 human plasma were untargeted, whereas those of RAW264.7 cells were targeted.

Sample Descriptions

RAW 264.7 / Mouse / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	Yes		

NIST SRM 1950 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) BMP[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	BMP	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS ² Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
HG(GPG,209)			
HG(GPG,227)			
-(-H)			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
FA1(+O) + HG(GP,155)			
FA2(+O) + HG(GP,155)			
FA1(+O) + HG(GP,137)			
FA2(+O) + HG(GP,137)			
FA1(+O) + HG(GPG,229)			
FA2(+O) + HG(GPG,229)			
FA1(+O) + HG(GPG,211)			
FA2(+O) + HG(GPG,211)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

1) BMP[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

2) LPC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
HG(PC,224)			
-(CH3+HCOO)			
FA1(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

2) LPC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

3) LPE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

3) LPE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

4) LPG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPG	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
FA1(+O)			
-FA1(-H)			
-FA1(+HO)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

4) LPG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

5) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPI	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
HG(PI,241)			
P(79)			
-FA1(+HO)			
FA1(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

5) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

6) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPS	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
P(79)			
P(97)			
-(C3H5NO2,87)			
FA1(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

6) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

7) PC O[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
-(CH3+HCOO)			
FA2(+O)			
FA1			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

7) PC O[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

8) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
HG(PC,168)			
-(CH3+HCOO)			
-FA1(+HO)-(CH3+HCOO)			
-FA2(+HO)-(CH3+HCOO)			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
-FA1(-H)-(CH3+HCOO)			
-FA2(-H)-(CH3+HCOO)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

8) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

9) PC P[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC P	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
-(CH3+HCOO)			
FA2(+O)			
FA1			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

9) PC P[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

10) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
HG(PE,196)			
HG(PE,140)			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
-FA1(+HO)			
-FA2(+HO)			
-FA1(-H)			
-FA2(-H)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

10) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

11) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
HG(PE,196)			
FA1			
FA2(+O)			
-FA2(+HO)			
-FA2(-H)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

11) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

12) PG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
HG(PG,171)			
HG(PG,227)			
FA1(+O)			
-FA1(+HO)			
-FA1(-H)			
FA2(+O)			
-FA2(+HO)			
-FA2(-H)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

12) PG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

13) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
HG(PI,241)			
HG(PI,241)-(H ₂ O)			
HG(PI,297)			
P(79)			
-FA1(-H)			
FA1(+O)			
-FA1(+HO)			
-FA2(-H)			
FA2(+O)			
-FA2(+HO)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

13) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification

14) PS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 2 and area > area error
MS Level for identification	MS ²	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Double bond position	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
MS ² adduct	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
-(C3H5NO2,87)			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
-FA1(-H)-(C3H5NO2)			
-FA1(+HO)-(C3H5NO2)			
-FA2(-H)-(C3H5NO2)			
-FA2(+HO)-(C3H5NO2)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	C=C position identification based on RT-DB with LC=CL
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		

14) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	Relative quantification